

FORMATION OF INSTITUTIONAL INFRASTRUCTURE FOR PROMOTION OF AGROTOURISM ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND SUPPORT ACTIVITIES.

Musakhanov Is The Son Of Kazikhan Abdulkhakim

Independent researcher of Namangan
Institute of Engineering and Technology

Phone: +998930524271

Email: musakhanovqozikhon@gmail.com

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Abstract: The article provides agrotourism services for private owners of villages by encouraging and supporting agrotourism business activities, issues related to solving problems such as expansion of focused economic activity, reduction of unemployment, creation of new jobs, additional income and improvement of socio-economic conditions. illuminated.

Key words: agrotourism entrepreneurship, infrastructure, standard of living of the population, employment, service sector.

The institutional infrastructure for the promotion and support of agrotourism entrepreneurship is formed by a complex of industries and spheres of activity that implements macroeconomic regulation of the regional economy and supports the most optimal macroeconomic ratios for the development of agrotourism entrepreneurship. in the region.

The main principles of agrotourism entrepreneurship are determined by the following, cooperation between state authorities, local self-government bodies and the private sector is determined by a number of basic legislation and regulatory legal documents. If we determine the main forms of interaction between the state and business, developed to one degree or another in the field of agrotourism entrepreneurship in the regions of Namangan region, they are as follows.- cooperation in the development of tourist clusters;

- cooperation of state and local authorities with self-regulating organizations;
- cooperation at the local level on the development of the social infrastructure of villages and the support of initiatives of rural communities to start their own business in the field of agrotourism entrepreneurship.

From the point of view of entrepreneurship, the expansion of economic activities aimed at providing agrotourism services for private owners of villages will reduce the unemployment rate, create new jobs, get additional income and socio-economic related to solving the problems of improving conditions. will lead to the improvement of the economic situation of the rural population.

This is confirmed by the fact that agrotourism entrepreneurship has long been considered as an alternative to agriculture in world practice. Amount of profit received. Also, the development of rural tourism infrastructure does not require large capital investments like other types of tourism, and can be carried out at the expense of rural residents themselves without additional investments. The study of the processes of promotion of entrepreneurial activity in the field of agrotourism entrepreneurship should be carried out

with the help of the analysis of the existing internal aspects of the regulation of the specified process and the study of foreign experience on this issue.

It is necessary to analyze the types and forms of entrepreneurial activity in the field of agrotourism entrepreneurship and the influence of the state on their development. Thus, the state has a strong influence on the development of agritourism business entities, as it determines the conditions in the tourist services market, finances or encourages the attraction of investments for the implementation of agritourism business projects, and supports the entities. protects the activities of the tourism business and their interests, affects the level of income of the population, determines the conditions of operation of the agrotourism business facilities.

Therefore, the state's encouragement of the development of agrotourism entrepreneurship and the level of support for this sector determine the scope of tourist flows in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan, especially in the regions of the Namangan region.

Summarizing the work of scientists and the results of their own research made it possible to clarify the means of state regulation of agrotourism business entities.

To date, scientists have not come to a single opinion about the main goal of state regulation of tourism development, stressing the need to "create a modern highly efficient and competitive tourist complex" "Ensuring a significant increase in the economic, social and ecological standard of living of the population" "Socially effective for the development of territories" , a convenient market that is economically viable and environmentally sound formation of the environment. and "creating favorable conditions for entry and development of domestic tourism" to the tourism business

The current mechanism for encouraging entrepreneurial activity in the field of agrotourism entrepreneurship is a system of institutional forms, management methods and economic tools implemented at the regional level to ensure effective entrepreneurial activity and the development of agrotourism entrepreneurship in the regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Picture-1. Tools of the mechanism for stimulating entrepreneurship in the field of agrotourism entrepreneurship at the regional level.¹

The effectiveness of the introduction of this mechanism will depend on its gradual implementation.

The main stages of the implementation of the mechanism for encouraging entrepreneurship in the field of agrotourism entrepreneurship are as follows:- analysis of the level of provision of natural resource potential of the region;

- Determination of criteria for promoting entrepreneurial activities in the field of agrotourism entrepreneurship;
- Control over promotion of entrepreneurial activity in the field of agrotourism entrepreneurship;

¹ О внесенні змін у Закон України "Про туризм". No. 1282-IV horse 18 November 2003 Electronic resource. The regime is available at: <http://www.rada.gov.ua/cgi-bin/laws/main.cgi>

- Measures to increase the efficiency of the mechanism of stimulating entrepreneurial activity in the field of agrotourism entrepreneurship. In accordance with the proposed stages of stimulation of entrepreneurial activity in the field of agrotourism entrepreneurship, we determine the criteria for such stimulation. In our opinion, such criteria are the level of safety of using the existing natural resource potential, the level of activity of rural green tourism entities, the level of influence of their activities on the development of the region, etc.

In conclusion, an important aspect of encouraging entrepreneurial activity in the field of agrotourism entrepreneurship is the selection and implementation of methods and means of stimulation. Taking into account the uniqueness of our research, the mechanism of entrepreneurial activity in the field of agribusiness can achieve positive results by introducing organizational and economic methods of stimulating entrepreneurial activity in the agricultural sector. We consider it appropriate to consider the main means of such stimulation in more detail. Research shows that one of the main economic aspects is the financial support of entrepreneurial activities in the field of agrotourism entrepreneurship.

References:

1. Bespartochny B.D., Khromova A.V. Peculiarities of marketing research in the field of agrotourism of the region // Fundamental research. 2015 year. No. 2. Part 2. P.339-342.
2. Durovych A.P. Marketing in tourism. Minsk: Novoe znanie, 2006. 496 p.
3. Ermachenkova O.A. Marketing research in tourism // Young student. 2014 year. No. 4. P.513-515.
4. Zaburanna L.V. Marketing research of the portrait of owners of rural green tourism objects // Rural green tourism. 2012. No. 2. B.6-10.
5. Kudla N.E. On the application of a complex of marketing measures in rural tourism // Economy of Ukraine. 2011 year. No. 2. B.79-85.
6. Cuzio N.E., Kosar N.S. Marketing support for the development of rural green tourism in Ukraine // Marketing and Innovation Management. 2017 year. Number 2. P.369-381.
7. Lipchuk V., Lipchuk N. Agrotourism: organizational and economic principles of development. Lviv: SPOLOM, 2008. P.131.
8. Bustonov M.M. Digital economy in improving the quality of economic growth// European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine. ISSN 2515-8260 2020.Vol 07, Issue 07. <https://www.scopus.com/results/authorNamesList.uri?sort=count-f&src> (SCOPUS).
9. Bustonov M.M. Macroeconomic Trends and Patterns of Sustainable Economic Growth and its Quality// Test Engineering & Management. 2019. November-December. <http://www.testmagazine.biz/index.php/testmagazine/article/view/221>
10. Bustonov M.M. The Firm Aspects and conditions Providing the Qualities of Economic Growth in Uzbekistan //International Journal of Economic Theory and Application. 2017, 4(4): 32-39 <http://www.aascit.org/journal/archive2?journalId=918&paperId=4704>
11. Bustonov M.M., Ensuring Long-Term Economic Growth in the World and Econometric Analysis of Economic Growth of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the Context of Extensive, Intensive and Digital Economy. Miasto Przyszłości Kielce 2022, ISSN-L: 2544-980X. <https://miastoprzyszlosci.com.pl/index.php/mp/article/view/406>

12. Bustonov M.M., Analysis of Economic Growth in the Juglyar Cycle in World Countries. Web of Scholars: Multidimensional Research Journal (MRJ) Volume: 01 Issue: 03 | 2022 ISSN: (2751-7543) <http://innosci.org/index.php/wos/article/view/53/37>
13. Bustonov M.M. Digital Economy In Improving The Quality Of Economic Growth. European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine ISSN 2515-8260 Volume 07, Issue 07, 2020.
14. Bustonov M.M. The firm aspects and conditions providing the qualities of economic growth in Uzbekistan. International Journal of Economic Theory and Application. 2017/ <http://www.aascit.org/journal/Ijeta>
15. Bustonov M.M. Macroeconomic Trends and Patterns of Sustainable Economic Growth and its Quality. // Test engineering & Management November-December 2019.
16. Bustonov M.M. Digital Economy In Improving The Quality Of Economic Growth. European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine ISSN 2515-8260 Volume 07, Issue 07, 2020.
17. Bustonov M.M. The Firm Aspects and conditions Providing the Qualities of Economic Growth in Uzbekistan. International Journal of Economic Theory and Application. 2017/ <http://www.aascit.org/journal/Ijeta>
18. B. Baykhanov, Bustonov M.M. Econometric models of sectoral distribution of investments in the economy of Uzbekistan. SOUTH ASIAN Journal of Marketing and Management Research 2019
19. Bustonov M.M. Macroeconomic Trends and Patterns of Sustainable Economic Growth and its Quality. TEST ENGINEERING & MANAGEMENT Vol. 81: Nov/Dec 19 Publication Issue: Vol 81: Nov/Dec 19 Issue Publication Date: 31 December 2019 Published: 2019-11-22
20. Bustonov M.M.,Maxmudov B.J., Rakhimov B.I. Directions for improving the efficiency of the monitoring of commercial banks loan commitments. A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal, Vol. 6 Issue 5, May 2020 Page No.: 304-310. <http://journalnx.com/journal-article/20151021>
21. Bustonov M.M.,Abdurakhmanova M. Organization of credit obligations and monitoring of commercial banks. ACADEMICIA An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. ISSN: 2249-7137 Vol. 10 Issue 5, May 2020 Impact Factor: SJIF 2020 = 7.13
22. Bustonov M.M.,Abdurakhmanova M. Main Directions of Improvement of the Process of Investment. International Journal on Integrated Education, Volume 3, Issue VI, June 2020 |18. e-ISSN : 2620 3502 p-ISSN : 2615 3785// <http://journals.researchparks.org/index.php/IJIE/article/view/395>
23. Bustonov M.M.,Maxmudov B.J., Rakhimov B.I. Basic concepts of the theory of uncertain sets and actions related to investment processes. International Engineering Journal For Research & Development. Vol. 5 No. 5 (2020): IEJRD, PUBLISHED: 2020-07-17
24. Rakhimov B.I., Bustonov M.M. Determination of the level of risks in investment projects using econometric model. International Journal of Innovations in Engineering Research and Technology [ijiert] issn: 2394-3696 website: ijiert.org volume 7, issue 8, aug-2020. Impact Factor: SJIF 2020 = 7.525
25. Bustonov M.M.,Digital economy in improving the quality of economic growth. European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine ISSN 2515-8260 Volume 07, Issue 07, 2020

26. Bustonov M.M.,Maxmudov M., Improving Economic Mechanisms to Encourage Efficient Use of Industrial Production Power in Kashkadarya Region/ Annals of R.S.C.B., ISSN:1583-6258, Vol. 25, Issue 3, 2021, Pages. 8183 - 8196 Received 16 February 2021; Accepted 08 March 2021.
27. Rakhimov B.I., Bustonov M.M. Analysis of monitoring and fulfillment of credit obligations in commercial banks/ International Journal of Business, Law, and Education Volume 02, Number 02, 2021. file:///C:/Users/admin/Desktop/16-Article%20Text-61-1-10-20210524%20(1).pdf
28. Bustonov M.M.,Ensuring Long-Term Economic Growth in the World and Econometric Analysis of Economic Growth of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the Context of Extensive, Intensive and Digital Economy. Miasto Przyszłości ISSN-L:2544-980X Table of Content - Volume 26 (Aug 2022)
29. Bustonov M.M., Analysis of Economic Growth in the Juglyar Cycle in World Countries. Vol. 1 No. 3 (2022): Web of Scholars : Multidimensional Research Journal Analysis of Economic Growth in the Juglyar Cycle in World Countries
30. Bustonov M.M., Digitalization and Economic Growth. Miasto Przyszłości ISSN-L: 2544-980X Vol. 30 (2022): file:///C:/Users/Lenovo/Desktop/201-206+Digitalization+and+Economic+Growth.pdf
31. Bustonov M.M., Implementation of the single complex cluster system in the territory of Uzbekistan. EURASIAN JOURNAL OF ACADEMIC RESEARCH Innovative Academy Research Support Center UIF = 8.1 | SJIF = 5.685 www.in-academy.uz Volume 2 Issue 13, December 2022 ISSN 2181-2020
32. Bustonov M.M., Economic growth: theoretical and practical aspect. EURASIAN JOURNAL OF ACADEMIC RESEARCH Innovative Academy Research Support Center UIF = 8.1 | SJIF = 5.685 www.in-academy.uz Volume 2 Issue 13, December 2022 ISSN
33. Bustonov M.M.,Digital economy in improving the quality of economic growth. European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine ISSN 2515-8260 Volume 07, Issue 07, 2020
34. Bustonov M.M.,Maxmudov M., Improving Economic Mechanisms to Encourage Efficient Use of Industrial Production Power in Kashkadarya Region/ Annals of R.S.C.B., ISSN:1583-6258, Vol. 25, Issue 3, 2021, Pages. 8183 - 8196 Received 16 February 2021; Accepted 08 March 2021.
35. Bustonov M.M. Digital economy in improving the quality of economic growth// European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine. ISSN 2515-8260 2020.Vol 07, Issue 07. <https://www.scopus.com/results/authorNamesList.uri?sort=count-f&src> (SCOPUS).
36. Bustonov M.M. Macroeconomic Trends and Patterns of SustainableEconomic Growth and its Quality// Test Engineering & Management. 2019. November-December. <http://www.testmagzine.biz/index.php/testmagzine/article/view/221>
37. Ishimbayev R.N. Criteria and principle of capability // Miasta Przyslosci 29, P 334-337
38. Ishimbayev R.N. Competitiveness of small business // Science and innovation. International scientific journal 1 (ISSUE 8), P 90-96
39. Ishimbayev R.N. CLASSIFICATION OF THE ASSESSMENT METHODS OF THE COMPETITIVENESS OF A SMALL BUSINESS // EURASIAN JOURNAL OF ACADEMIC RESEARCH 2 (Issue 13), P 1065-1070

40. Ishimbayev R.N. Ways to increase the competitiveness of enterprises // Central Asian Journal of Innovations on Tourism Management and Finance. (2023) Vol 1.4. P. 174-177
41. Ishimbayev R.N. Ways to Increase competitiveness of small enterprises and private enterprises in Uzbekistan // MIASTO PRZYSZŁOŚCI. (2023) Vol 1 P. 346-349.
42. Ishimbayev R.N. Critries and assessment of competitiveness of small business // Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Instituti of Engineering and Technology. (2022) Vol 7 P. 471-480
43. Залозная Г.М, Ишимбаев Р.Н. // Эволюция теоретических концепций конкуренции // Журнал экономической теории, 2014. № 4 С. 211-221
44. Ишимбаев Р.Н. Конкурентоспособность: понятие, значение и сущность // Международный научно-образовательный электронные журнал «Образование и наука в XXI веке». 2022. Том 4. №33. С. 67-71
45. Ишимбаев Р.Н. Факторы, влияющие на развитие конкурентоспособности малого бизнеса и частного предпринимательства в Узбекистане. // Академические исследования в современной науке. 2022. Том 1. №19. С. 62-68
46. Ишимбаев Р.Н. Бизнес-экосистема как фактор повышения конкурентоспособности предприятия на рынке. // Miasta Przynoslsci. 2022. Том 30. С. 376-377
47. Ишимбаев Р.Н. Акцент на конкурентоспособность малого и частного предпринимательства. // Машинасозлик илмий-техника журнали. 2022. №6 С. 684-689
48. Ишимбаев Р.Н., Холмирзаев А.Х. Цифровизация малого и среднего предпринимательства в Узбекистане. Экономика и социум. 2021. № 7 (86). С. 304-307.
49. Ишимбаев Р.Н. Холмирзаев А.Х. Сущность деятельности малого бизнеса и важность развития. // Экономика и социум. 2021. №7 С. 520-526

